

Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme and Spin

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In a previous note, we argued that for a free particle there exists a function $A(x,t)$ such that $d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p$ ((1a)) and $d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E$ ((1b)). In particular, we used $p=E(v)/v$ for the relativistic case and $p=mv$. We showed that $A(x,t)$ is the classical action for a free particle $\int dt L = T L$ with $v=x/t$ before the derivatives are taken. After, x/t is set to v . As a result, there is a nonrelativistic $A(x,t) = T \cdot 5mvv$ and a relativistic one $A = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} (c=1)$. We argued that ((1a)) and ((1b)) are in the form of flow equations. Energy E flows through space out of a dx region (i.e there is an energy flux Ev) so if x is held constant, the change in time is $-E$. We also noted that one may obtain both the Schrodinger and Klein-Gordon equations from ((1a)) and ((1b)) (see reference in (1)). As a result, $A(x,t)$ is linked to both the nonrelativistic and relativistic free particle actions, yields free particle quantum mechanical equations and may also be used to obtain the form of special relativity (as discussed in the reference in (1)).

In this note, we wish to consider spin which is not present in ((1a)) and ((1b)). For both relativistic and nonrelativistic classical dynamics which are linked to $A(x,t)$ one deals with numbers (scalars) and so no notion of spin arises. In obtaining both the relativistic Klein-Gordon equation and nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation from ((1a)) and ((1b)), one creates an eigenvalue equation i.e. $i d/dt \exp(i \text{Action}) = E \exp(i \text{Action})$ ((2a)) and $-i d/dx \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$ ((2b)) which only hold for the free particle. One may then use E and p in expressions $EE = pp + m_0 m_0$ (where $p=Ev = d\text{Action}/dx$ partial) and $E = pp/2m + V(x)$ where $p=mv = d\text{Action}/dx$ partial). For the free particle, one has ((2a)) and ((2b)) without establishing the Klein-Gordon equation. Given that $p=Ev$ is a vector, one may try to write ((2b)) as a vector, but given that one has operators acting on $\exp(i \text{Action})$ one does not use a basis vector e_i ($e_i \cdot e_i = 1$), but rather a "basis" operator or a spin matrix. Thus, we argue that spin emerges in this way without having to linearize the Klein-Gordon equation. Interestingly, this approach only holds for fermions. For the photon, which is a boson, a Dirac-like equation may be obtained directly from a $d/dt (\text{partial}) E L E L + B B + b \text{grad} \cdot (E I \times B) = 0$ as shown in (2) (with a, b being constants). This again follows from a flow scheme.

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Following from a Flow Scheme

In (1), we argue that both relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle classical mechanics and quantum mechanics follow from a flow scheme, namely:

$$d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \quad ((1b))$$

For the relativistic case, $p=Ev$ while for the nonrelativistic one $p=mv$. We start with an unknown function $A(x,t)$ and show that it is equivalent to the classical action $\int dt L$ where L is the Lagrangian. Thus, there is spatial flow from a dx region described by a Gauss-like one dimensional equation $d/dx (\text{partial}) A = p$, but at the same time, the dx region loses energy E in dt so $d/dt (\text{partial}) A = -E$.

Interestingly, there are two solutions to these equations namely classical mechanics and quantum mechanics (both relativistic and nonrelativistic). In the quantum case, however, one creates an eigenfunction solution which has far reaching consequences i.e.

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((2b))$$

((2a)) and ((2b)) only hold for a free particle and create “energy” and “momentum” operators with eigenvalues E and p. Applying the operator twice yields expressions for EE and pp. Thus one may convert classical mechanical conservation energy expressions (for a free particle) into eigenfunction equations $EE = pp + mm$ and $E = pp/2m + V$. (In the case of a potential, one considers a statistical distribution of $\exp(ipx)$ values i.e. $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$). Given the solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which holds for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases (although E and p have different meaning), one sees periodicity, two dimensions, dx and dt values related to $1/p$ and $1/E$ and interference of probability as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ seems to represent a kind of conditional probability. For a free particle, one has solutions directly from ((2a)) and ((2b)). As a result, there is no need to use the Klein-Gordon or free particle Schrodinger equation. (If one adds a potential, however, one needs these equations.)

At this point, no notion of spin has arisen. In the next section, we consider spin as arising from recognizing three-space together with ((2a)) and ((2b)) with no notion of linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation.

Spin and Three Space

Traditionally spin does not appear in the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation and seems to have been added by hand by W. Pauli. For the relativistic case, it did not emerge theoretically (it was already known experimentally) until P. Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation.

If one considers ((2a)) and ((2b)) they appear as scalar equations with the magnitude of p being used (E is already a scalar). One may always treat p as being a vector pointing in the z direction and think in terms of one dimension, but there is still the notion of three-space. In such a case, p is 3-vector and there are flows in all three directions p_x , p_y and p_z . If one decides to consider three-space, p becomes a vector in normal situations with a basis vector e_i such that $e_i \cdot e_i = 1$. For the eigenfunction situation, however, $-i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action})$ and one does not use a basis function approach, but rather basis operators or matrices.

$-i \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$ the momentum operator becomes:

$$-i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \rightarrow -i \alpha_j \frac{d}{d x_j} \quad \text{where } x_j = x, y, z \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore, there is a constraint on the alpha matrices such that:

$$\{ -i \alpha_j \frac{d}{d x_j} \} \cdot \{ -i \alpha_j \frac{d}{d x_j} \} = -\frac{d}{d x} \frac{d}{d x} - \frac{d}{d y} \frac{d}{d y} - \frac{d}{d z} \frac{d}{d z} \quad ((4))$$

Thus the alpha matrices would not appear in a Klein-Gordon equation. The constraint ((4)) leads to Pauli matrices (or 4x4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices as derived by P. Dirac.) As noted, they appear as the operator version of the basis vectors e_i if one wishes to acknowledge three-space and not restrict oneself to one dimension. Even though the magnitude of p lies in one direction, the vector itself exists in three so there is no reason not to consider 3-space.

As a result of the new matrix operator $\alpha(j)$, there is a new solution as one needs not only $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but a vector as well. This leads to new physical states associated with the recognition of three-space. Traditionally spin is associated with angular momentum within a quantum free particle. Interestingly, this angular momentum is only linked to 3-space, not to the momentum, and so has a fixed value and only holds for fermions for the constraint ((4)).

Thus, we argue that one does not need to necessarily linearize the Klein-Gordon equation, but that a flow scheme which uses the free particle action $A(x,t)$ to obtain both classical mechanics and quantum mechanics (relativistic and nonrelativistic) may be generalized in the quantum case to lead to spin. Moreover, spin seems to be directly linked to the recognition of 3-space as we have argued in previous notes.

The Photon Boson

As noted above, the approach used to introduce spin leads to Pauli matrices for $\alpha(j)$ and these apply to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ objects. Thus the above approach seems to be linked to fermions. Bosons (integer spin objects) also exist in 3-space and so it is surprising that the above approach (or the linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation as in the P. Dirac case) only yields spin solutions for fermions. In this section, we consider the photon which is a boson with spin 1. The Klein-Gordon equation or ((2a)) and ((2b)) predict $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ behaviour for all quantum objects and this seems to hold for the boson -photon. In order to see photon spin one needs more complicated equations, namely Maxwell's electromagnetic equations which yields a more complex flow equation (albeit a flow scheme):

$$a \frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) \{ E_i \cdot E_i + B \cdot B \} + b \text{grad} \cdot E_i \times B = 0 \quad ((5))$$

Here E_i is the electric field vector, B the magnetic field vector and a, b constants

In (2), we show that one may factor out an $E_i - iB$ term to obtain an equation for $E_i + iB$ which is taken to be the equivalent of the free particle photon (boson) wavefunction like $\exp(iA)$. The final equation involves a term $\epsilon_{ijk} \frac{d}{dx(i)}$ where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol and $x_i = x, y, z$. Thus, one again has the three directions in space as in the above sections with the basis vector replaced by a matrix operator namely ϵ_{ijk} where i refers to the i th matrix (x, y, z) and jk are the entries within the matrix. As a result, the argument is very similar to the Dirac form as has been noted already in the literature. What is different is that one needs a particular equation ((5)) which only holds for a particular boson, namely the photon. The basic idea of spin being linked to 3-space recognition still holds, but Maxwell's laws force three-space recognition because E_i and B exist in a plane perpendicular to the photon's motion. One cannot simply consider a one-dimensional space in the direction of p because E_i and B would not be part of such a space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to extend the free particle flow scheme d/dt (partial) Action = $-E$ and d/dx (partial) Action = p which yields free particle relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics to include spin. To do so, we argue that one cannot consider one dimension even though the magnitude of p which is all that appears in the flow equations is in one dimension. One needs to recognize 3-space and so the flow equation d/dx (partial) Action = p should be modified. Actually, one modifies the associated eigenfunction equation because that pertains to quantum mechanics i.e.

$$-i d/dx \longrightarrow -i \alpha(j) d/d x_j \quad \text{where } x_j=x,y,z$$

$\alpha(j)$ instead of being the basis vector e_j such that $e_j \cdot e_j=1$ becomes a basis operator linked directly to 3-space. This means that the solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ becomes modified to include a vector. A constraint exists such that pp does not include the effects of 3-space because it is a magnitude i.e.

$$\{ -i \alpha(j) d/d x_j \} \cdot \{ -i \alpha(j) d/d x_j \} \rightarrow pp$$

This leads to a rule which yields $\alpha(j)$ as the Pauli matrices (or 4x4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices as derived by P. Dirac.). Interestingly these only hold for spin $\frac{1}{2}$. What about bosons? In this note, we consider the case of the photon. A flow scheme and the recognition of 3-space still exist, but one needs a more complicated equation which follows from Maxwell's em equations namely: d/dt partial $a(EI \cdot EI + B \cdot B) + b \text{ grad} \cdot EI \times B = 0$. As shown in (2), this is equivalent to an equation linear in $EI+iB$ with a term $e_{ijk} d/dx_i$ where e_{ijk} is the Levi Civita symbol which serves as the basis operator like $\alpha(j)$ the Pauli matrix (or 4x4 matrix containing the Pauli matrices).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Photon Wave Equation from Continuity Equation with Poynting Vector (preprint, zenodo, 2021)